

Obtaining the Tsallis Distribution from $e/T \ll 1$ and $e/T \gg 1$ Considerations?

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In this note, we try to obtain the Tsallis distribution in the following manner. We first assume that there exists a parameter q such that for $q=1$, the Tsallis distribution yields the Maxwell-Boltzmann for any e/T value. We then assume that $1-q$ represents a deviation from the $q=1$ MB result and suggest that $(1-q)e/T$ would increase the weight of $e/t \gg 1$ power series expansion terms of $\exp(-e/T)$ so that they do not drop as fast as $\exp(-e_i/T)$. Finally, we assume that for $e/T \ll 1$, the Tsallis and Maxwell-Boltzmann unnormalized results are the same for any q . We then show that these assumptions, linked to physical ideas, lead to the Tsallis distribution. We are not aware of this approach having been used in the literature, but it is possible that it has already appeared.

Maxwell-Boltzmann Distribution and $e/T \gg 1$

The Maxwell-Boltzmann distribution: $f(e) = C(T) \exp(-e/T)$ ((1)) has a very sharp drop-off from $e/T \gg 1$. If one wished to lessen it, one might introduce a parameter q such that $(1-q)$ increases the $e/T \gg 1$ terms in a power series expansion of $\exp(-e_i/T)$ with $q > 1$. One may suggest that for $q=1$, one obtains the MB result.

On the other hand, since the above considerations focus on $e/T \gg 1$, one may suggest that for $e/T \ll 1$ and any q value, the MB and Tsallis results are the same. Using these assumptions, we try to see if the Tsallis distribution may be obtained.

First, we note that the form ((1)) holds for the MB case and one should also be able to write the Tsallis result as an exponential:

$$\exp\{ F((1-q)e/T, 1-q) \} \quad ((2))$$

A problem which now arises is that for $q=1$, one should obtain the MB result, but $1-q$ for $q=1$ is 0 and so the variable $(1-q)e/T$ vanishes when it should not. This suggests that there should be a mathematical procedure which removes the $1-q$. We reiterate that the $1-q$ factor is present to modify e/T so that it does not drop as quickly as $\exp(-e/T)$ for $e/T \gg 1$.

For $e/T \ll 1$, one should be able to expand the function F such that all $1-q$ terms cancel and one is left with $\exp(-e/T)$. Given that one has the variable $(1-q)e/T$, one requires a $1/(1-q)$ in the $e/T \ll 1$ expansion. Thus:

$$\text{For } e/T \ll 1 \text{ one needs } 1/(1-q) \text{ multiplied by } -(1-q)e/T \quad ((3))$$

$$(1-q)e/T \text{ for } e/T \ll 1, \text{ however, is the first term of the well-known expansion of } \ln(1+x) = x \quad ((4))$$

$$\text{Thus, one may consider: } \exp\{ 1/(1-q) \ln [1 - (1-q)e/T] \} \quad ((5))$$

as a possible solution. This satisfies the $e/T \ll 1$ condition of obtaining the MB distribution for any q , but must be tested for $q=1$ for any e/T . In such a case, we consider the $q=1$ limit of the argument of $\exp(\)$.

Limit $q=1$ of $1/(1-q) \ln(1 - (1-q)e/T)$ requires l'Hopital's Rule ((6))

Limit $q=1$ of ((6)) = $-1 e/T$ ((7))

Thus, one obtains $\exp(-e/T)$ for the $q=1$ limit, i.e one recovers the MB result. This approach and ((5)) yields the MB case for any q and $e/T \ll 1$ as well as the MB case for $q=1$. Furthermore, $(1-q)$ is a factor which enhances e/T for $e/T \gg 1$ and $q > 1$, reducing the sharp $\exp(-e/T)$ decline for $e/T \gg 1$.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we propose a method for obtaining the Tsallis distribution based on a specific physical idea of reducing the sharp decline of $\exp(-e/T)$ for $e/T \gg 1$. We suggest introducing a parameter q , such that $(1-q) e/T$ is enhanced by $q > 1$, but insist on the Maxwell-Boltzmann result for $q=1$ and also for any q with $e/T \ll 1$. This approach leaves $e/T \ll 1$ distribution values unchanged from the MB case for any q , but changes $e/T \gg 1$ leading to a less sharp drop. At the same time, $q=1$ yields the MB case for all e/T values.

Using these assumptions, we have shown above that: $f(e) = [1 - (1-q)e/T]^{-1/(1-q)}$ is such a distribution, i.e. the Tsallis distribution satisfies these criteria.